

OPTIMIZATION OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES' PRODUCTION CAPACITIES THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND MACHINE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract

The article examines the use of digital transformation (DT) and machine learning (ML) technologies for optimizing the production capacities of industrial enterprises. The advantages of integrating modern digital solutions, such as Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence, and manufacturing execution systems (MES), which significantly enhance the flexibility, adaptability, and efficiency of production, are highlighted. The methods of applying ML algorithms for predicting equipment performance, identifying hidden anomalies, and reducing the risk of malfunctions are analyzed. It is emphasized that digital twins and cloud technologies contribute to improved resource management and cost reduction.

Keywords: digital transformation (DT), machine learning (ML), optimization, production capacities, industrial enterprises, Internet of Things (IoT), digital twins.

Introduction

Modern industrial enterprises operate in conditions of increasing competition and accelerating technological changes. In this context, one of the priorities is to optimize production capacities, which ensures not only increased economic efficiency, but also sustainable development of organizations. The main challenges faced by companies include the need to increase the flexibility of production processes, reduce costs and improve product quality.

Digital transformation (DT), based on the introduction of new technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), allows us to solve these problems. The purpose of this article is to analyze how DT and the use of machine learning (ML) technologies as a class of AI methods contribute to optimizing the production capacities of industrial enterprises.

The main part. Overview of DT technologies in industry

The process of integrating digital technologies into all aspects of an enterprise is called DT. The main purpose of such changes is to increase the flexibility and adaptability of the business, improve productivity

and optimize internal and external processes. DT covers not only the introduction of new technologies, but also changes in corporate culture, decision-making approaches and management strategies.

The rapid adoption of digital transformation in industry has been greatly influenced by the significant impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. Mandatory limitations and social distancing regulations have caused a necessity to discover novel methods for sustaining production processes and engaging with clients. Businesses aimed to uphold competitiveness and sustainability by proactively integrating digital technologies for automation and remote management of production. In contemporary times, one of the main factors in digital transformation is the utilization of cutting-edge technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT), big data, cloud computing, and AI. These technologies enable the gathering and examination of vast quantities of data, streamlining daily tasks, and enhancing the efficiency and precision of production activities. In 2023, the price of DT hit \$2,15 trillion. Statista predicts that by 2027, this amount will increase to \$3,9 trillion, as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Forecast of growth in spending on DT technologies and services worldwide, trillion dollars [1]

One of the significant achievements in the field of modern technological solutions is the use of digital twin technologies and production management systems (MES). **Digital twin technology** is a virtual model of a physical object or system that allows you to test and

optimize processes without interfering with real production. This reduces risks and increases the effectiveness of innovation. In 2020, the manufacturing industry accounted for more than 22% of the digital twins market. It was followed by the automotive industry with an

indicator of 18%. According to forecasts, by 2025, the market volume in the manufacturing industry will exceed \$6 billion [2]. **MES** combines data from various stages of the production cycle. They combine planning and execution, which ensures more transparent and efficient process management. According to Global Market Insight, the MES market volume in 2023 was estimated at more than \$13,5 billion, and the average annual growth rate was more than 9,5% between 2024 and 2032 [3].

Traditional methods of managing production processes based on manual operations, static control systems and intuitive decision-making are becoming less effective. Given the complexity of production chains, the increase in data volumes and high requirements for flexibility, these approaches are not able to provide the necessary adaptation and responsiveness. On the contrary, digital management methods demonstrate significantly higher efficiency (table 1).

Table 1

Comparison of traditional and digital methods of production management [4]

Criterion	Traditional methods	Digital methods
Process flexibility	Low; processes are strictly fixed; it is difficult to adapt production to changing conditions; requires significant time, effort, and resources for changes.	High; due to the use of real-time data and adaptive algorithms, processes can quickly adapt to changing demand and conditions.
Decision-making	Decision-making is based on the experience and intuition of specialists, which can be subjective and limited.	Use of analytical data and AI algorithms ensures objectivity and accuracy in decision-making.
Production monitoring	Limited monitoring capabilities; control is often conducted manually or with outdated systems, which reduces the speed of response to issues and failures.	Automated monitoring using IoT and digital twins allows all processes to be monitored in real time and adjustments to be made promptly.
Resource management	Resource management often relies on static, outdated planning systems, leading to inefficient use of materials and resources.	Optimized resource management using digital systems allows for effective reallocation and minimizes waste, improving overall operational efficiency.
Costs	High costs due to low productivity, longer decision-making cycles, and frequent errors in production processes.	Reduced costs due to process optimization, use of resources, and minimization of production errors.
Accuracy and errors	High probability of errors due to human factor and outdated systems with limited accuracy.	Reduced errors due to automated systems and algorithms that increase accuracy and minimize the impact of the human factor.

In the context of rapid technological development and the complexity of production processes, traditional management methods are losing their effectiveness, which requires a revision of approaches to the organization and management of production. DT provides new opportunities to increase productivity and adaptability through the integration of advanced solutions. This allows enterprises to quickly adapt to changing conditions, effectively manage resources and reduce costs through automation and accurate forecasting.

Machine learning in industry

The role of ML in modernizing production processes and increasing their efficiency is significant. Being a subset of artificial intelligence, it relies on the use of algorithms and models that can learn from data and improve their predictions and decisions without direct programming. This allows businesses to predict different scenarios and make informed decisions.

In 2023, the ML market in the USA amounted to just over \$55 billion. This came after several unstable years of growth and recession from 2020 to 2022. Starting in 2024, the market is expected to grow steadily by almost \$15 billion per year, without taking into account any unforeseen circumstances such as pandemics that could destabilize growth forecasts [5].

The main ML algorithms used in industry include regression methods, classification, clustering, and deep learning algorithms. **Regression methods** are used for

predicting performance metrics and time series analysis, enabling advanced production volume planning and efficient inventory management. **Classification algorithms** assist in defect detection and product quality analysis based on sensor and image data analysis. **Clustering algorithms** are applied for data segmentation, which helps improve the management of production processes and the analysis of production deviations.

Deep learning, utilizing multilayer neural networks, is widely applied in computer vision and natural language processing tasks. In the industry, this enables the automation of product quality control by analyzing product images in real-time and detecting defects with high accuracy. The implementation of such technologies minimizes the risk of errors, increases productivity, and reduces the defect rate, significantly improving the overall performance of the production line.

The impact of ML on productivity and product quality is undeniable. The **automation of monitoring processes and predictive analytics** allows for the timely detection of potential equipment failures and the planning of preventive maintenance [6]. This reduces downtime and ensures more stable operations, directly influencing the overall productivity of the enterprise. ML also contributes to the optimization of raw material and energy resource usage through accurate demand forecasting and adaptive production planning, which leads to cost reduction and increased profitability.

Examples of industrial enterprise production capacity optimization using DT and ML

In recent years, American companies have been actively implementing DT and ML technologies to improve the efficiency of their production capacities. For example, **Honeywell**, a well-known manufacturer in the field of industrial automation, implemented the Batch Historian system, which provided the ability to integrate historical data to improve the analysis and management of production operations. This solution

not only accelerated the processes of data collection and processing, but also increased overall efficiency through automated data analysis and timely decision-making. This allowed the company to maintain a high level of productivity and minimize delays in the production process. Honeywell's 2023 report mentions that the company achieved revenue growth of 3%, increasing it to \$36,7 billion, and operating profit amounted to \$7 billion (fig. 2).

Figure 2. Honeywell economic performance [7]

The implementation of digital technologies has allowed the company to strengthen its position and create redundancy mechanisms to adapt to a difficult economic environment. This approach not only optimizes production capacity, but also maintains Honeywell's long-term sustainability and flexibility.

fied data access, and increased productivity through improved analysis of manufacturing data. MDC provides the ability to analyze in a cloud environment, ensuring the efficiency and flexibility of manufacturing process management. The integration of modern technologies has enabled the company not only to improve the management of existing resources, but also to expand the range of its activities. This has led to the development of new areas, including innovative approaches to production and improved methods of interaction with customers, which has helped strengthen P&G's position in the global market (fig. 3).

Another example is **Procter & Gamble (P&G)**, one of the world's largest manufacturers of consumer goods. The company uses cloud solutions Predix Manufacturing Data Cloud (MDC) from GE Digital to optimize its manufacturing operations. The use of cloud technologies has reduced infrastructure costs, simpli-

Figure 3. Comparison of Procter & Gamble's business lines in 2010 and 2023 [8]

According to Procter & Gamble's 2023 report, the growth in financial performance was driven by sustainable development in a challenging economic environment. The company's revenue increased to \$82 billion, up 2% year-on-year. Organic earnings per share increased 2%, despite significant raw material costs and currency fluctuations. These achievements highlight

the successful application of DT and productivity strategies, which allowed the company to adapt to external challenges and strengthen its financial position.

An example of an American company that actively uses modern technologies to improve the efficiency of its production processes is **Ford**. The use of augmented

reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) in assembly operations allows engineers not only to visualize potential design errors, but also to conduct detailed analysis of complex components, improving the accuracy and quality of assembly. These technologies also contribute to improving staff training by creating a safe environment for learning new skills and procedures. As a result of the introduction of such innovative approaches, Ford was able to reduce the number of production errors, which, in turn, contributed to a significant increase in workstation productivity and improved the quality of final products at the global level.

According to Ford's report for 2023, total global sales reached approximately 4,413 million vehicles, which shows significant growth compared to previous years [9]. The introduction of modern technologies has helped to increase productivity and reduce the number of errors in production processes. This allowed the company to improve product quality and maintain a high level of operational efficiency.

Conclusion

The introduction of DT and ML technologies can significantly improve the efficiency of production processes in industrial enterprises. Automation of monitoring, performance forecasting and resource management using adaptive algorithms contribute to timely identification of potential failures, reduction of downtime and improvement of overall production stability. In addition, the use of deep learning methods for analyzing sensor and image data helps to minimize the percentage of defects and improve product quality, which has a positive effect on the profitability of the enterprise.

The integration of innovative solutions such as IoT technologies, digital twins and production MES opens up new opportunities for flexible production process management and resource optimization. This not only reduces costs and increases economic efficiency, but also ensures more sustainable development of the enterprise in the face of increasing competition and rapid technological changes.

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